

THEORY OF ELECTRON TRANSMISSION IN SEMICONDUCTOR STRUCTURES WITH ALTERNATING ASYMMETRIC POTENTIAL WELLS AND BARRIERS

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Abstract. The propagation of electron waves in a medium with varying properties along a specified direction has been theoretically analyzed. This approach utilizes the one-electron stationary Schrödinger equation based on the law of energy conservation. As a result, the elastic scattering processes of non-interacting, spinless particles, including those occurring via the tunneling effect, were consistently described.

Keywords: semiconductor structure, Schrödinger equation, elastic scattering, tunneling effect, potential barriers, quantum well, effective mass, bulk quantization.

Аннотация. Теоретически проанализировано распространение электронных волн в среде с изменяющимися свойствами по определенному направлению. Подход основывается на стационарном уравнении Шрёдингера для одного электрона с учетом закона сохранения энергии. В результате последовательно описаны процессы упругого рассеяния независимых друг от друга бесспиновых частиц, включая процессы, происходящие за счет туннельного эффекта.

Ключевые слова: полупроводниковая структура, уравнение Шрёдингера, упругое рассеяние, туннельный эффект, потенциальные барьеры, квантовая яма, эффективная масса, размерное квантование.

Annotatsiya. Ma'lum yo'nalishda xossalari o'zgaruvchi muhitda elektron to'lqinlarining tarqalishi nazariy jihatdan tahlil qilindi. Bunda energiyaning saqlanish qonuni asosida bir elektronli stasionar Shredinger tenglamasidan foydalanildi. Natijada, spinsiz va o'zaro ta'sirlashmaydigan zarralarning elastik sochilishi, shu jumladan tunnel effekti orqali sodir bo'ladigan jarayonlar izchil tarzda tavsiflandi.

Kalit so'zlar: yarimo'tkazgichli struktura, Shredinger tenglamasi, elastik sochilish, tunnel effekti, potensial to'siqlar, kvant o'ra, effektiv massa, hajmiy kvantlanish.

We will consider general issues related to the propagation of electron waves in a medium with properties that vary only along a specific direction. The approach is based on the use of the single-electron stationary Schrödinger equation to describe elastic scattering and tunneling processes of non-interacting spinless particles, assuming conservation of their total energy.

Modern technology enables the fabrication of semiconductor layers with an arbitrary composition profile (quantum well structures) to enhance the characteristics of devices based on them [1]. In this case, the problem of electronic states reduces to the behavior of a microparticle in a periodically varying potential field. Let the potential energy of electrons be described by the relation $U(x) = U_1$ for $x < x_1$ and $U(x) = U_2$ for $x > x_1$. Then the electronic wave function is sought in the form:

$$\psi_j(x) = A_j \exp(ik_j x) + B_j \exp(-ik_j x), \quad (1)$$

where $k_j(x) = k_j = \sqrt{\frac{2m_j(E-U_j)}{\hbar^2}}$ is the wave vector, m_j is the effective mass of the electrons, and $j = 1, 2, 3, \dots$ denotes the layer numbers in the structure. Then, from the boundary conditions for the continuity of the wave functions [2] and electron flux, taking into account Bastard's conditions (see, for example, [3])-which differ from standard quantum mechanical problems - it is straightforward to obtain relations connecting the amplitudes of the de Broglie waves of electrons located in adjacent regions (layers):

$$\begin{aligned} 2A_1 &= (1 + a_{21})A_2 \exp(i(k_2 - k_1)x_1) + (1 - a_{21})B_2 \exp(i(k_2 + k_1)x_1), \\ 2B_2 &= (1 - a_{21})A_2 \exp(i(k_2 + k_1)x_1) + (1 + a_{21})B_2 \exp(i(k_2 - k_1)x_1). \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Here $a_{jj'} = \frac{\tilde{k}_j}{\tilde{k}_{j'}}$, where $\tilde{k}_j = \frac{k_j}{m_j}$. Equation (2) can conveniently be rewritten using the transfer matrix from region "1" to "2":

$$\begin{bmatrix} A_1 \\ B_2 \end{bmatrix} = \hat{T}^{(21)} \begin{bmatrix} A_2 \\ B_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} T_{11}^{(21)} & T_{12}^{(21)} \\ T_{21}^{(21)} & T_{22}^{(21)} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} A_2 \\ B_2 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (3)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} T_{11}^{(21)} &= T_{22}^{(21)*} = \frac{1}{2}(1 + a_{21})e^{i(k_2 - k_1)x_1}, \quad T_{12}^{(21)} = T_{21}^{(21)*} = \frac{1}{2}(1 - a_{21})e^{-i(k_2 + k_1)x_1}, \\ \det[T^{(21)}] &= \tilde{k}_2 / \tilde{k}_1 = \sqrt{\frac{m_1 E - U_2}{m_2 E - U_1}}. \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

The transfer matrix $T^{(21)}$ becomes a unimodular matrix in the case when $\tilde{k}_2 = \tilde{k}_1$, i.e., for symmetric structures [3], where the potential barrier heights and the effective electron masses are equal.

If we introduce the reflection coefficient r and transmission coefficient t as the ratios of the probability current densities in the reflected and transmitted waves to the probability current density of electrons in the incident wave, then by definition

$$r^{(21)} = |B_1|^2 / |A_1|^2 = \left| \frac{T_{21}^{(21)}}{T_{11}^{(21)}} \right|^2 \quad \text{and} \quad t^{(21)} = \frac{\tilde{k}_2}{\tilde{k}_1} \frac{|A_2|^2}{|A_1|^2} = \frac{\tilde{k}_2}{\tilde{k}_1} \frac{1}{|T_{11}^{(21)}|^2}.$$

In this context, the transmission coefficient has physical significance in classically allowed regions, where the electron wave vectors are real values. Then, for the potential chosen in our case, we have

$$r^{(21)} = |\tilde{k}_1 - \tilde{k}_2|^2 / |\tilde{k}_1 + \tilde{k}_2|^2 = \left| 1 - \frac{\sqrt{\frac{m_1 E - U_2}{m_2 E - U_1}}}{1 + \sqrt{\frac{m_1 E - U_2}{m_2 E - U_1}}} \right|^2.$$

In particular, for a symmetric structure, $r^{(21)} = \frac{|1 - \sqrt{m_1/m_2}|^2}{|1 + \sqrt{m_1/m_2}|^2}$, and it becomes zero when the effective electron masses are identical across all layers of the structure.

Currently, three-layer structures with rectangular quantum wells, featuring an additional potential dip in the center, are used to create a new generation of resonant-tunneling diodes and heterolasers with separated electronic and optical confinement [1]. Therefore, we will further analyze a structure composed of three layers, described by the potential $U(x) = U_1$ for $x < x_1$ and for $x_1 \leq x \leq x_2$; $U(x) = U_3$ for $x > x_2$ and $U(x) = U_2$ for $x > x_1$. Then, the transfer matrix $T(31) = T(32)T(21)$, with its matrix element

$$\begin{aligned} T_{11}^{(31)} &= T_{11}^{(32)}T_{11}^{(21)} + T_{12}^{(32)}T_{21}^{(21)} = \frac{1}{4} \exp(ik_3 x_2 - k_1 x_1 - k_2(x_2 - x_1)) \times \\ &\times \{(1 + a_{21})(1 + a_{32}) \exp(2ik_2(x_2 - x_1)) + (1 - a_{21})(1 - a_{32})\}. \end{aligned}$$

Then, for the over-barrier transmission coefficient of electrons, we have

$$t_{n.b.}^{(31)} = 4\tilde{k}_1\tilde{k}_2^2\tilde{k}_3 \left\{ (\tilde{k}_2^2 + \tilde{k}_1\tilde{k}_3)^2 - (\tilde{k}_1^2 - \tilde{k}_2^2)(\tilde{k}_3^2 - \tilde{k}_2^2) \cos^2[k_2(x_2 - x_1)] \right\}^{-1}. \quad (5)$$

From (5), it is evident that, firstly, $t_{n.b.}^{(31)}$ is invariant under the transformation $\tilde{k}_1 \leftrightarrow \tilde{k}_3$, which means that the electron transmission coefficient in the structure does not depend on the direction from which the electrons approach the barrier. Secondly, the over-barrier transmission exhibits an oscillatory nature. This oscillation is associated with the interference of waves reflected from the potential barrier, with its amplitude determined by the difference $(\tilde{k}_1^2 - \tilde{k}_2^2)(\tilde{k}_3^2 - \tilde{k}_2^2)$, and it vanishes when electrons have energies

$$E_j^{(0)} = (m_2U_j - m_jU_2)/(m_2 - m_j), j = 1,3.$$

From (5), it is evident that dimensional quantization can be observed in the electron spectrum. If such a spectrum is defined by the formula $E_-(k_y, k_z, n_-) = E(k_y, k_z) + U_2 + E_0n_-^2$, then structures with such layers, where $\tilde{k}_1 = \tilde{k}_2 = \tilde{k}_3$ with $\tilde{k}_2 = \frac{\pi n_-}{2(x_2 - x_1)}$, will be tunneling-transparent, i.e., $t_{n.b.}^{(31)} = 0$, where n_- are odd integers. Interestingly, if the dimensional quantization spectrum is defined by the formula $E_+(k_y, k_z, n_+) = E(k_y, k_z) + U_2 + E_0n_+^2$, then in structures with layers where n_+ are even integers, the behavior of $t_{n.b.}^{(31)}$ depends on both the heights of the potential barriers and the ratio of the effective masses of electrons in adjacent layers, i.e., it is determined by the expression

$$4\tilde{k}_1\tilde{k}_2^2\tilde{k}_3 \{ (\tilde{k}_2^2 + \tilde{k}_1\tilde{k}_3)^2 - (\tilde{k}_1^2 - \tilde{k}_2^2)(\tilde{k}_3^2 - \tilde{k}_2^2) \}^{-1},$$

where, for $\tilde{k}_1 > \tilde{k}_2 > \tilde{k}_3$ (or $\tilde{k}_1 < \tilde{k}_2 < \tilde{k}_3$), it is possible that $t_{n.b.}^{(31)} > 1$. This indicates that, in such a structure, an enhancement of the transmission of electron de Broglie waves may occur.

Thus, depending on the nature of the dimensional quantization chosen, it is possible to either suppress or enhance the oscillatory scattering phenomena from barriers or tunneling through the barrier.

For the study of under-barrier transmission of electrons, one can use the above formula for $T_{11}^{(31)} = T_{11}^{(32)}T_{11}^{(21)} + T_{12}^{(32)}T_{21}^{(21)}$, where, for $E > U_j$ (for $j = 1,3$) and $E < U_2$, it is convenient to make the following transformation:

$$\tilde{k}_j \pm \tilde{k}_2 = \tilde{k}_j \pm i\kappa_2 = \sqrt{\tilde{k}_j^2 + \kappa_2^2} \exp(\pm i\phi_{j2}),$$

where $\phi_{j2} = \arctan\left(\frac{\kappa_2}{\tilde{k}_j}\right)$ and $\kappa_2 = \sqrt{\frac{2m_2}{\hbar^2}(U_2 - E)}$. Then, the under-barrier transmission coefficient has the form:

$$t_{n.b.}^{(31)} = 4\tilde{k}_1\tilde{k}_2^2\tilde{k}_3 \{ (\tilde{k}_2^2 + \tilde{k}_2^2)(\tilde{k}_2^2 + \tilde{k}_2^2) \sinh[\kappa_2(x_2 - x_1)] \}^{-1} \quad (6)$$

and is symmetric with respect to the transformation $\tilde{k}_1 \leftrightarrow \tilde{k}_3$.

Furthermore, it should be noted that in an asymmetric (and even in a symmetric structure, but with different effective electron masses in different regions (layers)) semiconductor structure, oscillations are expected in the spectral dependence of both the transmission coefficient, i.e., the tunneling effect, and the transparency coefficient of the potential barrier. This oscillation is due to the interference of waves reflected from the potential barrier, with its amplitude determined by the difference between the wave vectors of electrons located on the potential barrier and in the adjacent potential wells.

It should also be noted that this interference phenomenon in the structure does not disappear even in a symmetric structure due to the difference in effective electron masses in various regions of the structure.

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